

Basicity and Constitution of Some Inorganic Acids from Electric Conductivity and Coagulation Experiments.

BY W. V. BHAGWAT AND N. R. DHAR.

In a recent paper (Dhar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 585), it has been shown that fluoride and iodate ions behave practically as divalent ions. In this communication we have tried to throw light on the basicity and constitution of some inorganic acids by measurements of the electric conductivity and coagulating powers of their respective sodium or potassium salts.

Hypophosphorous Acid.

Kahlbaum's pure hypophosphorous acid was neutralised with pure caustic soda and a stock solution was obtained. The exact concentration of the sodium hypophosphite solution was determined by oxidizing a known volume of the solution to phosphate by fuming nitric acid and weighing as $Mg_2P_2O_7$.

The following results were obtained in the measurements of equivalent conductivity of a solution of sodium hypophosphite at 30°.

Equivalent conductivity ...	51.4	68.4	82.2	92	100.5	105.6
Concentration ...	N/6815	N/1363	N/2726	N/5462	N/10904	N/21804
Equivalent conductivity ...	110.05	112.6	115.07	116.2	116.7	
Concentration ...	N/43608	N/87216	N/174432	N/348864	N/697728	

From this we find that $\mu 697.7 - \mu 21.8 = 11.1$.

Hence the acid appears to be monobasic.

Coagulation Experiments.

$Fe_2O_3 = 4.88$ g. per litre.	$ZrO_2 = 10.84$ g. per litre.
$CeO_2 = 6.16$,, ,, ,,	$Cl_2 = 0.7506$,, ,, ,,

Sol	Amt. taken. (c.c.)	Total volume (c.c.)	KCl required for coagulation.	Sodium hypophosphite required for coagulation.	Ratio of KCl to sodium hypophosphite.
Fe(OH) ₃	1	10	2 c.c. N/20	1.2 c.c. N/68	5.6
Ce(OH) ₄	1	5	1.4 c.c. N/5	0.4 c.c. N/20.6	14.42
Zr(OH) ₄	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	0.6 c.c. N/20.6	8.9

The experimental results on conductivity measurements with sodium hypophosphite show that $\mu_{697.7} - \mu_{0.6815} = 65.25$, whilst the difference between equivalent conductivities of potassium chloride and potassium fluoride between $N/1001.4$ and $N/0.9843$ is 42.1 and 41.5 respectively. These results seem to show that hypophosphorous acid has a tendency to be dibasic and this conclusion is supported from the coagulation experiments. The coagulating power of sodium hypophosphite is about eight times greater than that of potassium chloride on $Zr(OH)_4$ sol, fourteen times greater with $Ce(OH)_4$ and six times greater with $Fe(OH)_3$. It should, however, be mentioned here that the coagulating power of caustic soda or potash on these sols is much greater than that of potassium chloride because alkalis react chemically on the peptising electrolytes which lead to the stabilisation of these sols.

Cornec (*Ann. Chim. Phys.*, 1913, *viii*, 29, 490) measured the lowering of the freezing point of solutions of hypophosphorous acid when progressively neutralised with sodium or ammonium hydroxide. The resulting simple curve is characteristic of monobasic acids. From the heat of neutralisation of hypophosphorous acid by sodium or barium hydroxide Thomsen concluded that it is a monobasic acid.

Our experiments on electric conductivity and coagulation show that the acid is monobasic with a slight tendency to be dibasic.

Phosphorous Acid.

Kahlbaum's pure phosphorous acid was neutralised with pure sodium hydroxide and the exact strength was determined in the same way as hypophosphorous acid.

The following results were obtained with electric conductivity measurements and coagulation with sodium phosphite solutions:—

Concentration.	μ	Concentration.	μ
N/3.792	110.3	N/120.544	181.6
N/7.584	127.7	N/241.086	189.5
N/15.068	142	N/482.176	197.5
N/30.136	156.4	N/964.352	201.6
N/60.272	169.5	N/1928.704	205.2

Coagulation Experiments.

$\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 4.88$ g. per litre
 $\text{CeO}_2 = 6.16$ g. ,, ,,
 $\text{ZrO}_2 = 10.34$ g. ,, ,,

Sol.	Amount. (c.c.)	Total volume. (c.c.)	KCl reqd.	Sodium phos- phite.	Ratio of KCl to sodium phosphite.
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$	1	5	2 c.c. N/20	0.6 c.c. N/454	75.6
$\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_3$	1	5	1.4 c.c. N/0.5	1 c.c. N/130	36.4
$\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_3$	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	2 c.c. N/130	16.9

Cornec (*ibid.*, 1913, *viii*, 30, 63) measured the lowering of freezing point of solutions of phosphorous acid when progressively neutralised by sodium or ammonium hydroxide and observed two breaks in the curve corresponding with the dibasicity of the acid; this conclusion is in agreement with Thomsen's thermochemical observations.

Italiener ("Beiträge zur Kenntnis der phosphorigen Säure und ihrer Salze," Freiburg i. Br., 1917) has concluded from freezing and boiling points measurements that phosphorous acid is markedly polymerised and exists as $(\text{H}_3\text{PO}_3)_2$ and the complex molecule is ionised. Thus:—
 $\text{H}_6\text{P}_2\text{O}_6 \rightleftharpoons \text{H}^\circ + \text{H}_3\text{P}_2\text{O}_6'$ and $\text{H}_6\text{P}_2\text{O}_6 \rightleftharpoons 2\text{H}^\circ + \text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_6''$.
 If we calculate the values of i from the freezing-point lowering and boiling-point elevation measurements of Italiener on the basis that phosphorous acid exists as H_3PO_3 , the following results are obtained:—

i from F.P.	1.84	1.54	1.52	1.66
Concentration	... 1.186	0.539	0.296	0.148
i from B.P.	... 0.93	1.02	1.17	1.9
Concentration	.. 0.976	0.488	0.244	0.122

Now if phosphorous acid existed as $\text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_6$ and it is ionised as $\text{H}_6\text{P}_2\text{O}_6 \rightleftharpoons 2\text{H}^\circ + \text{H}_4\text{P}_2\text{O}_6''$, as has been assumed by Italiener, the values of i at the concentrations of 0.148 and 0.122 would have been 3.32 (F.P.) and 3.8 (B.P.) respectively. However, according to the assumption of Italiener, the number of ions available from the polymerised molecules of phosphorous acid is three and not four, which is approximately the experimental value. Hence it appears that the conclusion of Italiener is doubtful. Our results on electric

conductivity and coagulation show that phosphorous acid behaves as a dibasic acid with a slight tendency to be tribasic.

Iodic Acid

Kahlbaum's pure potassium iodate was several times recrystallised from conductivity water and the following results were obtained:—

Dilution	...	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Equivalent conductivity at 21°	...	90.1	93.95	97.29	100.45	103.4	105.95

From these we find that $\mu_{1024} - \mu_{32} = 15.85$, a value which is higher than ten. Hence iodic acid appears to have a marked tendency to be dibasic. It has also been observed that the conductivity of potassium iodate does not become constant even at a dilution of 1024. This is in agreement with our view that iodic acid and iodates exist partly in the polymerised condition. Our results are not in agreement with those of Walden ("Leitvermögen der Lösungen," 1924, Vol. II, p. 113) who obtained the value 11.9 for $\mu_{1024} - \mu_{32}$ with potassium iodate at 25°. The following are the results of the coagulation experiments:—

$\text{CeO}_2 = 6.16$ g. per litre. $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 11.43$ g. per litre.
 $\text{ZrO}_2 = 10.34$ g. per litre. $\text{Cl} = 0.7506$ g. per litre.

Sol.	Amount. (c.c.)	Total volume. (c.c.)	KCl required.	KIO ₃ required.	Ratio of KCl to KIO ₃ .
Ce(OH) ₃	1	5	1.4 c.c. N/5	0.6 c.c. N/125	58
Zr(OH) ₃	1	,,	1.8 ,, N/5	1.6 ,, N/125	20.3
Fe(OH) ₃	1	,,	1.5 ,, N/5	1.0 ,, N/108	35.4

Hence the coagulating power of iodate ion is of the same order as that of a bivalent ion.

Titanic Acid.

Kahlbaum's potassium titanate was washed with alcohol to remove free alkali. The following results were obtained on the coagulation of some hydroxide sol by potassium titanate. In order to get

comparable results, the same sols were coagulated by potassium sulphate under identical conditions:—

$ZrO_2 = 10.34$ g. per litre. $Fe_2O_3 = 11.4$ g. per litre.

Sol.	Amount (c.c.)	Total volume (c.c.)	KCl required.	Potassium titanate.	Ratio of KCl to potassium titanate.
Zr(OH) ₄	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	3.3 c.c. N/220	19
Fe(OH) ₃	1	5	1.5 c.c. N/5	2.9 ,, N/220	22.8

$ZrO_2 = 10.34$ g. per litre. $Fe_2O_3 = 11.4$ g. per litre.

Sol.	Amount taken (c.c.)	Total volume (c.c.)	KCl required.	K ₂ SO ₄ reqd.	Ratio of KCl to K ₂ SO ₄ .
Zr(OH) ₄	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	1 c.c. N/100	26
Fe(OH) ₃	1	5	1.5 c.c. N/5	0.8 c.c. N/100	37.5

Hence titanate ion behaves as bivalent ions towards the coagulation of some hydroxide sols.

Antimonic Acid.

The following results were obtained in the coagulation of some hydroxide sols by K₂H₂Sb₂O₇.

$CeO_2 = 6.16$ g. per litre.

$ZrO_2 = 10.34$ g. ,, ,,

$Fe_2O_3 = 11.45$ g. ,, ,,

Sol.	Amount taken (c.c.)	Total volume (c.c.)	KCl required.	Potassium antimonate required.	Ratio of KCl to potassium antimonate.
Ce(OH) ₃	1	5	1.4 c.c. N/5	1.5 c.c. N/200	37.3
Zr(OH) ₄	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	3.2 c.c. N/200	16.2
Fe(OH) ₃	1	5	1.50 c.c. N/5	0.8 c.c. N/100	37.5

The coagulation experiments are in favour of the view that potassium pyroantimonate gives out a bivalent ion in solution. The electric conductivity measurements of Tornula (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, **118**, 84) with potassium antimonate show a slight decrease of conductivity on dilution. Similar results were obtained with sodium vanadate.

Boric Acid.

The following results were obtained on the electric conductivity measurements with solutions of pure borax at 21°.

Dilution	...	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Equivalent conductivity	...	55.3	51.1	66.5	70.8	74.9	77.5	80	82

Hence $\mu_{1024} - \mu_{32} = 15.5$. The same value ($\mu_{1024} - \mu_{32} = 15.5$) was obtained by Rosenheim (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1921, **119**, 26) with $K_2B_4O_7$ solutions at 0°.

The results of the coagulation experiments are as follows:—

$$ZrO_2 = 10.34 \text{ g. per litre.}$$

$$Fe_2O_3 = 11.43 \text{ g. per litre.}$$

Sol.	Amount taken. (c.c.)	Total volume (c.c.)	KCl required.	Borax required.	Ratio of KCl to borax.
Zr(OH) ₄	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	1.2 c.c. N/125	27
Fe(OH) ₃	1	5	1.5 c.c. N/5	1.0 c.c. N/125	37.5

It appears, therefore, that the negative ions given out from a solution of borax are bivalent.

Vanadic Acid.

The following results were obtained in the measurement of electric conductivity of sodium vanadate solutions at 21°.

Dilution	...	19	38	76	152	304
Equivalent conductivity	...	117.8	122.4	127	125.4	118.2

Düllberg (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1903, **48**, 129) obtained similar decrease of conductivity on dilution with a solution of $(NaVO_3)_3$.

The following are the results of coagulation experiments:—

$$CeO_2 = 6.16 \text{ g. per litre.}$$

$$ZrO_2 = 10.34 \text{ g. ,, ,,}$$

$$Fe_2O_3 = 11.43 \text{ g. ,, ,,}$$

Sol.	Amount taken. (c.c.)	Total volume. (c.c.)	KCl required.	Sodium vanadate required.	Ratio of KCl to sodium vanadate.
Ce(OH) ₃	1	5	1.4 c.c. N/5	2.2 c.c. N/380	48.3
Zr(OH) ₄	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	3.9 c.c. N/380	26.8
Fe(OH) ₃	1	5	1.5 c.c. N/5	1.1 c.c. N/160	48.7

The coagulation results show that vanadate ion is bivalent.

Tungstic Acid.

The conductivity results with solutions of sodium tungstate at 21° are as follows:—

Dilution	...	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Equivalent conductivity	...	77.6	82.9	87.3	91.3	95.3	99.1	101.3	103.9

Hence $\mu_{1024} - \mu_{32} = 16.6$ with sodium tungstate solution. Walden (*ibid.*, p. 117) found for $\mu_{1024} - \mu_{32}$ the value 21.5 with a solution of normal sodium tungstate.

The following results were obtained in the coagulation of some hydroxides with sodium tungstate.

$\text{CeO}_2 = 6.14$ g. per litre.
 $\text{ZrO}_2 = 10.34$ g. „ „
 $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 11.33$ g. „ „

Sol.	Amount taken (c.c.).	Total volume (c.c.).	KCl required.	Na_2WO_4 required.	Ratio of KCl to Na_2WO_4 .
Ce(OH)_3	1	5	1.4 c.c. N/150	0.9 c.c. N/5	46.6
Zr(OH)_3	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	1.8 c.c. N/150	2.2
Fe(OH)_3	1	5	1.5 c.c. N/5	0.8 c.c. N/125	47

Hence tungstate ion appears to be bivalent and tungstic acid is dibasic.

Molybdic Acid.

The following results have been obtained with potassium molybdate and ammonium molybdate solutions regarding electric conductivity at 21°.

Potassium molybdate.

Dilution.	..	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Equivalent conductivity.	...	108.5	113.7	119.8	125	128.8	132.5

Ammonium molybdate.

Dilution.	...	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
Equivalent conductivity.	...	84.5	96.45	108.8	120.9	128.6	136.9	143.5

Hence $\mu_{1024} - \mu_{32}$ for potassium molybdate = 24 and = 47.05 for ammonium molybdate.

Grossmann (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1904, **41**, 47) obtained the value 22.4 for $\mu_{1024} - \mu_{32}$ with a solution of sodium molybdate at 25°.

The coagulation experiments are as follows:—

$\text{CeO}_2 = 6.16$ g. per litre. $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 11.43$ g. per litre.
 $\text{ZrO}_2 = 10.36$ g. ,, ,,

Sol.	Amount taken (c.c.).	Total volume (c.c.).	KCl required ³ .	K-molybdate.	Ratio of KCl to K-molybdate.
$\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_4$	1	5	1.4 c.c. N/5	0.9 c.c. N/150	46.6
$\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_4$	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	1.8 c.c. N/150	22
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$	1	5	1.5 c.c. N/5	0.9 c.c. N/125	41.6

$\text{CeO}_2 = 6.16$ g. per litre. $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 11.43$ g. per litre.
 $\text{ZrO}_2 = 10.36$ g. ,, ,,

Sol.	Amount taken (c.c.).	Total volume (c.c.)	KCl required	Ammonium molybdate.	Ratio of KCl to ammonium molybdate.
$\text{Ce}(\text{OH})_4$	1	5	1.4 c.c. N/5	1.9 c.c. N/400	50
$\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_4$	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	3.7 c.c. N/400	28.1

We have carefully compared the electric conductivities of potassium chloride and fluoride under identical condition and the results are as follows:—

Concentration.	μ of KF.	μ of KCl	Concentration.	μ of KF.	μ of KCl.
N/0.9843	... 92.5	114.5	N/62.539	131.2	152.3
N/1.9886	. 102.3	122.5	N/125.068	. 132.7	154.3
N/3.976	.. 111.68	130.5	N/250.13	.. 133.5	155.6
N/7.942	.. 118.7	138.8	N/500.27	.. 133.8	156.4
N/15.63	124.1	143.9	N/1001.44	... 134	156.6
N/31.259	128	148	N/2002.88	... x	x

The conductivity measurements do not support the dibasic nature of hydrofluoric acid, although the coagulation experiments of Ghosh and Dhar (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, **44**, 149; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 303) with several sols are in favour of the bivalent nature of fluoride ion.

In previous papers (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 121, 99 ; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 585) evidence has been brought forward in favour of the view that chromic acid in solution exists mainly as H_2CrO_4 and potassium dichromate exists in solution chiefly as $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$. Evidently the coagulating power of potassium chromate should be greater than that of potassium dichromate, because the number of bivalent CrO_4^{--} ions will be greater in chromate solutions than in dichromate solutions of equivalent concentration. This conclusion appears to be supported by the following coagulation experiments with zirconium hydroxide sol:—

$\text{ZrO}_2 = 10.34$ g. per litre. $\text{Cl}_2 = 0.7506$ g. per litre.

Sol.	Amount taken (c.c.)	Total volume (c.c.)	Amount of KCl for coagulation.	Electrolyte for coagulation.	Ratio of KCl to chromate or dichromate.
$\text{Zr}(\text{OH})_2$	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	1.4 c.c. N/125 K_2CrO_4	23.2
„	1	5	1.3 c.c. N/5	2.2 c.c. N/125 $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$	14.8

Metallic Hydroxides.

From the electric conductivity, viscosity and cataphoretic measurements and other considerations it has been shown in these laboratories (*Faraday Soc. Discussion*, October, 1920 ; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1923, 27, 376 ; *Chem. News*, 1926, 133, 177 ; *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 152, 405 ; 1928, 174, 1) that when hydroxides of chromium, zinc, aluminium, tin, lead, beryllium, etc., are dissolved in sodium or potassium hydroxide they exist mainly as negatively charged colloids. We have determined the coagulating power of potassium hydroxide alone and potassium hydroxide containing different amounts of hydroxides of zinc, tin, aluminium, chromium and lead.

Hydroxides of these metals were prepared in cold and washed very carefully to free them from any electrolyte, and dissolved in the solution of potassium hydroxide. Then its coagulating power with a ferric hydroxide sol was determined. Similarly the coagulating power of potassium hydroxide alone was found. The experimental results are recorded below:—

Sol.	Hydroxide.	Concentration of the metallic hydroxide (g. per litre).	Amount of KOH (c.c.)	Amount of hydroxide added (c.c.)	Electrolyte for coagulation.	Concentration required.	Ratio to KCl.
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ containing 11.45 gms. of Fe_2O_3 in a litre.					KCl	1.5 c.c. N/5	1
"	$\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$	11.732 ZnO	10	10	KOH	0.5 c.c. N/63.77	38.26
"	$\text{Sn}(\text{OH})_4$	4.8 SnO_2	10	10	Zincate (on the assumption that no KOH formed zincate).	0.8 c.c. N/102.04	38.26
"	$\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$	2.84 Al_2O_3	10	10	Stannate conc. on the above assumption.	0.8 c.c. "	38.26
"	$\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$	8.32 Cr_2O_3	10	10	Aluminate conc. on the above assumption.	0.8 c.c. "	38.26
$\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ containing 4.28 gms. of Fe_2O_3 per litre.					Chromate conc. as above.	0.8 c.c. "	38.26
					KCl	0.6 c.c. N/10	1
					KOH	1.3 c.c. N/137.5	68.8
	$\text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$	22.3 PbO_2	10		Piumbate, conc. as above.	6 c.c. N/610.2	61

The experimental results show that the coagulating power of KOH does not change appreciably on the addition of the hydroxides of zinc, tin, lead chromium and aluminium. Hence these hydroxides appear to exist in the colloidal state in KOH. If zincate, plumbite etc. were formed the coagulating power of the solutions containing hydroxides would have been different from that of caustic potash itself.

Summary.

(1) In the case of hypophosphorous acid, electric conductivity and coagulation experiments with sodium hypophosphite show that the acid is monobasic with slight tendency to be dibasic, while in case of phosphorous acid although the results support the view that the acid is mainly dibasic with a slight tendency to be tribasic, it contradicts the view of Italiener that it exists as $(H_3PO_3)_2$ and ionises as $H_6P_2O_6 \rightleftharpoons 2H^+ + H_4P_2O_6''$.

(2) The view that the iodates exist partially in the polymerised state has been supported from conductivity measurements and coagulation experiments.

(3) Coagulation results with sodium or potassium salts of antimonic, titanio, boric, vanadic, tungstic, and molybdic acids show the bivalent nature of their negative ions.

(4) The coagulation experiments with chromates and dichromates are in favour of the view that chromic acid in solution exists mainly as H_2CrO_4 and potassium dichromate as $KHCrO_4$.

(5) The view that when the hydroxides of chromium, zinc, aluminium, tin, lead, beryllium etc., are dissolved in sodium or potassium hydroxide, they exist mainly as negatively charged colloids has been supported from the coagulation experiments with ferric hydroxide sol.

